

SITE GPR	YEAR 2012	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.529 Max: 62.680	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1416 ☐ Natural ☒ Anthropogenic	Gravel
In cross-section? ☐ Yes ☒ No		In elevation drawing? ☐ Yes ☒ No		Photos: ☒ Yes ☐ No #: 2654-56	Photo Model: ☐ Yes ☒ No #:	
DEFINITION bout layer below lifts 1411 + 1386			Covered by ☒ SU: 1386	Fills ☐ SU:	Filled by ☐ SU:	
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? ☒ Color ☒ Composition ☐ Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS ☐ Accumulation ☐ Construction ☐ Cutting ☐ Erosion ☐ Collapse ☒ Intentional deposition			
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (frequent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX clay % silt: 50% sand 50% ☒ Granular ☐ Layered ☐ Cohesive			
Anthropic		Geological		Organic		
☐ Pottery	☐ Nails	☐ Tuff (specify)	☐ Charcoal			
☐ Tiles	☐ Marble	☐ Travertine	☐ Ash			
☐ Amphorae	☐ Quarried debris	☐ Other Limestone	☐ Animal bones			
☐ Dolia	☐ Slag ☐ Brick	☐ Basalt	☐ Human bones			
☐ Mosaic tile(s)	☐ Basalt slabs	☐ Clay	☐ Animal teeth			
☐ Mortar	☐ Opus signinum	☐ Sand	☐ Human teeth			
☐ Coins	☐ Painted plaster	☐ Silt	☐ Shells			
☐ Metal (specify)	☐ Burnt Adobe	☐ Pebbles (range)	☐ Other (specify)			
☐ Collapse debris	☐ Other (specify)	☐ Gravel (range)				
☐ Glass						
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)						
Northern Limit		☒ Original ☐ Not Original ☐ Excavation Limit		Depth: ☒ Original ☐ Not Original		
Southern Limit		☒ Original ☐ Not Original ☐ Excavation Limit				
Western Limit		☒ Original ☐ Not Original ☐ Excavation Limit				
Eastern Limit		☒ Original ☐ Not Original ☐ Excavation Limit				
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE						
Is equal to:			Is bound to (only for masonry):			
Is abutted by:			Abuts:			
Is covered by: 1386, 1411			Covers:			
Is cut by:			Cuts:			
Is filled by:			Fills:			
OBSERVATIONS layer has not been excavated yet, is still visible						
DESCRIPTION Position within sector: south-eastern part of Trench B						
Shape: square						
For layers complete this section:						
Surface (slope direction, visible inclusions): /						
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope) /						
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):						
Nature of the interface with layer below: ☐ sharp ☐ diffuse ☐ commingled ☐ other (specify)						
For cuts complete this section:			Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):			
Cut edges: ☐ rounded ☐ straight						
Cut sides: ☐ straight ☐ concave ☐ convex ☐ sloping						
Cut bottom: ☐ flat ☐ concave ☐ irregular						
How is cut top edge? ☐ sharp ☐ rounded						
How is cut bottom edge? ☐ sharp ☐ rounded						
Observations:						

There is a little bag of finds from the first cleaning of this layer!

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) Irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material: Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify):

Size: Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cm

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations: Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

Floor/revetment type:

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing: Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:	Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)
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INTERPRETATION

SOIL SAMPLING: ☐ Yes ☐ No Total volume of layer (buckets): Sample quantity (buckets): Sample fraction (%)	NON SOIL SAMPLES: ☐ Yes ☐ No If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.): Size:	SIEVING: ☐ Yes ☐ No Total volume of layer (buckets): Sample quantity (buckets): Sample fraction (%)
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STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY ☐ Good ☒ Fair ☐ Poor	Filled-out by CHM	on	17.7.2012
	Revised by CMM	on	17-7-2012
	PDFd by ECR	on	18-7-2012
	Entered by	on	